

**A Geographical Study of Tourism Classification in Nashik District, Maharashtra State,
India**

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Abstract

In Nashik district, there is diversity in terms of tourism. Both religious and natural tourism centers are in the way of development in Nashik district and one can see that some of these religious tourism centers have been developed. Although this research paper is done from a descriptive point of view, it will help people to know what are the types and kinds of tourism available in Nashik district. Although various mediums and sources have been used for this research based on the secondary information, it has mainly used information from reference books and research papers on the internet and various websites.

Keywords: Tourism, classification, Potential, Human Resources, Nashik District

Contribution/Originality: While some tourist centers are awaiting development, Nashik district has a great deal of socio-cultural and environmental diversity. All these factors have affected the tourism business in the study area.

Introduction

The economy of a country is dependent on various trades mainly through direct and indirect exchange of goods. And tourism is an international trade or national trade which generates foreign exchange but does not involve direct exchange of goods. Also the local visa development of any area depends on the natural and human resources available there. This tourism business can provide a lot of employment to the local people and help in the regional development of a wide

range of things. However, there are different types of tourism, mainly natural tourism, religious, cultural, adventurous tourism, religious tourism, etc. Nashik district covers all these tourist centers. Socio-economic, geographical, technological, demographic and political factors are responsible for the development of tourism. There are many tourist destinations in the world that have not yet been explored by human beings or they are deprived of development but they can be developed if human beings know about such tourist destinations. Socio-economic, political and religious factors affect the development of any tourism. This tourism business promotes a lot of local and regional development as well as a large number of commodity purchases. This business generates a large number of different jobs and creates new markets. Although tourism is an invisible trade and money is transacted but not seen in the exchange of goods, tourists are considered to be an important factor. Natural resources are required for tourism development as much or more human resources are also required. There is no need for tourism in a place where there is no need for human development. In short, without human resources, there can be no tourism development of any kind.

Due to this, various tourist centers in Nashik district have been classified and their capacity has been studied in this research paper. This work is based on the secondary data as well as information presented from the point of view of theoretical approaches.

Study Area

The tribal area of the Nashik district is positioned between 19°34'39" N to 20°51'41" N latitudes and 73°14'15"E to 74°24'45" E longitudes. The area mainly covers western part of the Nashik District and includes seven tehsils namely Baglan, Dindori, Kalwan, Peint, Surgana, Trimbakeshwar and Igatpuri. The area has hilly topographic conditions with medium to high rainfall. In the area of study, two major rivers originate i.e. Godavari and Girana flowing eastward. The average height of the study area is 620 meters AMSL. Area is mainly eastward sloping and has an average slope of 7.13 degree. The total geographical area (TGA) of tribal tehsil is 6786 sq. km., which is about 43 percent of TGA of the Nashik district.

Map no 01: Location Map

Aims and Objectives

The most important aim is to study the tourist center in Nashik district. An assessment of tourism potential in Nashik District. Then the secondary objectives are as follows:

1. To do a geographical study of the tourist centers in Nashik district,

2. To classify the tourist centers in Nashik district,

The aims and objects of this research have been taken from a theoretical point of interpretation.

Methodology

This work is dependent on the secondary data. It mainly uses information research Articles, Books, Nashik District gazetteer, reports, and various information sources on the Internet. This information is also based on information from the internet/ website and other research papers.

Results and Discussion

1. Religious Tourism Center:

There is a lot of diversity in Nashik district from a religious point of view but Nashik district is famous for some temples in Nashik district in which eleven important temples are generally considered important for tourists. These temples have huge potential for tourism development, but some of these temples are not developed for tourists. Trambkeshwar is one of the most famous places in Nashik district. It has a 'Jyotirlinga' (There are only 12 such places in India) and it is also a place of Kumbh Mela (There are only 4 such places in India). People, mostly Hindus, from all over the world visit here for religious ceremonies. You can see that some tourist centers in Nashik city have been developed and Shree Saptshrungi Gad Wani has been developed religiously but the rest of the tourist centers are underdeveloped even though they have a lot of potential. The potential for development among the following religious tourism centers is as follows, Tapovan and Kalaram temple, Mangi Tungi Temple, Kushavart Tirtha, Shree Someshwar Temple, Dhammagiri – Vipassana Centre, Sita Gumphā etc. Other famous temples are Goddess 'Saptshrungi Devi' (Kalwan Tehsil), Goddess 'Renuka Devi' (Chandwad Tehsil), God Ganpati temples at Thengoda (Baglan), Khedgaon (Kalwan) and Navashya Ganpati (Nasik). Ancient Gondeshwar temple at Sinnar is one of the examples of great ancient Indian art but not so popular. It is a Hemadpanthi style temple. The Archeological Survey of India has been working on the restoration of this temple. Other

religious centers which have a potential of becoming a tourist centers are, Taked (Igatpuri tehsil), Jagdamba Mata temple (Kottam Gav - Yeola tehsil), Vipshyana center near Igatpuri, Chandanapuri near Malegaon.

2. Natural Tourist Places:

Nashik district is underdeveloped as a natural tourist destination. Due to the Sahyadri range to the west of the district, there is a large area of greenery, the lot of potential for natural tourism. The study area has a wide range of mountains in various forms and a large number of trekking sites have been developed. It mainly consists of the following tourist centers. Brahmagiri Hill, Salher Hill, Anjaneri hills, Gangapur Dam, Dudhsagar Falls, Dugarwadi waterfall and Vihigaon Waterfall. The study area has a lot of scope for the development of waterfalls and these centers can be developed here. In short, there is a lot of potential for the development of these natural tourism centers. Dudhsagar waterfall (< 30 mtr.) famous for its scenic beauty, located 8 km to the west of Nasik city at Someshwar. One of the major waterfalls lies west of Trambakeshwar called as Dugarwadi Waterfall (140 mtr.), It is 30 km west to Nasik city and 6 km. from Trambakeshwar. Few minor waterfalls also have local importance and located in the hilly track of weastern ghat mainly in Igatpuri, Trambak, Peth, Surgana, Kalwan and Bag,an tahsil (eg: Sangameshwar-Shirala waterfall-Peth, Saptshrungi gad waterfall- Kalwan, Dodheshwar waterfall- Baglan. But all the waterfalls are seasonal and depend on the monsoon rain.

3. Forts:

Nashik district has a historical background so a large number of forts have been built. There are many forts in Nashik district that tourists do not know or they are deprived of development. For the development of such forts, it is necessary to develop transportation in these areas. So that people can reach those forts. According to the Nashik District Gazeteer there are 25 forts in the districts and almost all are hill forts. But according to the MTDC website there are 38 forts. Major forts are Salher-Mulher, Ankai-Tankai, Ramshej, Dhodap, Hatgad, Ahivant etc. Others are Tilwan, Achala, Aundha Patta, Bahula, Bhaskargad, Chauler, Galna, Ghargad, Harish, Indrai, Kachna, Kanheri, Kankrala, Kantra, Koledhair, Manikpunj, Markinda, Pisol,

Bhorgad, Ratangad, Vaghera, and Tringalwadi fort. Most of them are damaged but still its historical value attracts the tourists.

4. Cultural or Heritage Tourism:

Nashik district has a large religious heritage including some of the Ramayana period antiquities, and so it is a culturally important tourist attraction. Pandavleni are the Buddhist rock-cut caves. They are a group of 24 caves in the Trirashmi hill (as known from the inscriptions), representing the Hinayana Buddhist caves. These caves contain inscriptions written in the Brahmi script using Prakrit language. These caves are located 8 km. to the southwest of Nashik city. At the same time, the number of tribal people is high in Nashik district, so tribal culture can be developed here or tribal culture can be developed in tourism centers. With proper guidance and proper planning, a cultural tourism center can be developed here, so there is a potential.

5. Other Attractions:

Due to the large-scale production of grapes in Nashik district, there is a large wine industry in the district. Students visit this area as an industrial visit to see the wine industry. For this, Industrial Visit Tourism can be developed as an educationally important tourist destination. There are also Coin Museums which are also devoid of people. In short, these museums are not known to the public but are visited by local tourists. There are also many adventure tourism centers in the district that can be developed. Zonkers Adventure Park, Deolali Camp, Shubham Water World, Shagun Resort & Water park, Arjun Adventure Park, There are other tourist centers in Nashik district but this tourist center is not known to people from other districts or other states so proper planning and planning is required to make people aware of this tourist center. It is visited by local tourists for various reasons but it needs to be developed from the point of view of people from outside the district or other states coming to visit this place. From that point of view, proper planning is needed.

Conclusion

Nashik district is a natural house, due to the Sahyadri mountain range running from the western side of the district, Godavari River originates here and the district also has a religious heritage. As a result, there is a huge potential for development for natural and religious tourism.

In addition, some of the tourist centers in Nashik district are deprived, even if the roads are developed and with the help of technology, the tourist centers can also be developed. There is a need to create awareness among the people as the culture of tourism is not yet developed as people are not aware of the benefits of tourism. Few tourist centers have been developed in Nashik district or more tourists visit those places. People or tourists do not go to other tourist places. Proper planning and policy for tourists to visit other places can create many jobs in rural areas.

References

1. Anil A. Landge (2017) Tourism potential in Akole tahsil of ahmednagar District (Maharashtra), International Journal of Researches in Social Sciences and Information Studies, Vol. V (1) PP 26-29.
2. Bharat L. Gadakh (2015) An Assessment of Tourism Potential: A Case Study of Nashik City, Maharashtra, *International Journal of Research in Geography 1(1)Pp 8-12*
3. Bhatia A.K (2007) International Tourism management, Sterling Publishers Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
4. Bhatia A.K (2007) The Business of Tourism (Concepts and Strategies), Sterling Publishers Pvt.ltd. New Delhi. P/p- 77 to 80
5. Chintaman Bhaguji Nigale (2018) Tourism Development Nashik City And Trimbakeshwar– A Micro Study, Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal, 7(7) Pp 90-97.
6. Dhattrak S.P (2018) Ecotourism potential of Pandavleni caves or Nashik caves, Nashik district, International journal of basic and applied research, 8(7), Pp 879-883
7. Gadekar D.J (2009) Scope of Adventurous tourism in Akole taluka Ahmednagar district, Research Analysis and evaluation International, Volume 2, Issue 18 Pp 42-43.
8. Gadekar Deepak Janardhan (2016) A Hybrid Land Cover Classification of Landsat-7 & 8 (OLI) ETM+ Data for Resourceful Vegetation Mapping - Akole Thasil Dist- Ahmednagar, M.S, India, American International Journal of Research in Humanities Arts and Social Sciences,13(3) 217-221
9. Gadekar Deepak Janardhan and Mhaske P. H (2018) A Study of Rainfall Characteristics in Ahmednagar District (Ms), Shodhankan International Journal, 1 (15) 35-39.
10. Kudnar N. S., (2019) Impacts of GPS-Based Mobile Application for Tourism: A Case Study of Gondia District, Vidhyawarta, Peer-Reviewed International Publication, PP-19-22.
11. Nitin Bajirao Borse (2017) Tourism Development in Nashik District: Potential and remedies, 'A Two Day Interdisciplinary International Seminar' On "Geographical & Historical Perspective Of Global Problem" At D. P. Bhosale College, Koregaon, Satara (India) , Pp 1-8
12. Nitinkumar M. Patil (2019) Tourism Potential in Akole Tehsil of Ahmednagar District, Maharashtra State, India, Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 9(2) Pp 128-132.

13. Nupur Panwar (2017) Assessment of Tourism Potential: A Case study of Alwar District, Rajasthan, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology,4(11)Pp189-196.
14. P.H Mhaske et al., (2011) Land Use & Economic Activity in Shirdi. Rahata Taluka, District Ahemadnagar M.H, International Referred Research Journal, Research analysis and Evaluation, 2(18) 75-76
15. Prem Nath Dhar (2000) International Tourism Kahishka Publishers Distribution, New Delhi.
16. S.D Gulave (2020) Use of Landsat ETM+ Data for Delineation of Vegetation Cover Area in Akole Thasil, , International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology, Volume 7, (2)57-61
17. Vasudev Shivaji Salunke (2020) Tourism Potential in Tribal Sub Plan Area of Ahmednagar District. Journal of Information and Computational Science 10(02) Pp 531-535

Website:

1. <https://tourismteacher.com/definition-of-tourism/>
2. <https://nashik.gov.in/tourism/tourists-places/>
3. <https://www.maharashtratourism.gov.in/destination/nashik>

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